

Low-intensity continuous ultrasound enhances the therapeutic efficacy of curcumin encapsulated exosomes derived from hypoxic liver cancer cells, a homotropic drug delivery system

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Abstract: Exosomes are cell-secreted extracellular nano-vesicles that can efficiently deliver therapeutic cargo for cancer treatment. However, since exosomes show low quantity and limited target-specificity, internal and external stress stimulation to increase exosome efficiency has been researched. Inspired by these studies, the uptake efficiency of Cobalt chloride-induced hypoxic cancer cell-secreted exosomes was evaluated, where western blots and RT-PCR data revealed increased exosome secretion and different protein composition exhibited by hypoxic H-Exos (Hypoxic exosome) compared to natural N-Exos (Normoxic exosome). Furthermore, these H-Exos were stimulated by low-intensity ultrasound continuously (LICUS), with an intensity of 360 mW/cm² and frequencies of 3 MHz in vitro and 1 MHz in vivo. Hyperthermic and mechanical stress caused by the ultrasound successfully improved exosome uptake via clathrin-mediated pathways, where confocal laser microscopy pictured strong internal localization near the target cell nuclei. Last, LICUS-equipped H-Exos were loaded with hydrophobic curcumin (H-Exo-Cur) and treated against parent HepG2 liver cancer cells. The UV-vis spectrophotometer displayed enhanced stability, solubility, and concentration of encapsulated drug molecules. In MTT and FACS studies, ~ 40 times higher cell death was induced, and in animal studies, ~ 10 times higher tumor sizes were suppressed by LICUS-assisted H-Exo-Cur than control. Collectively, with all advantages, the delivery platform constructed in this research demonstrates enormous therapeutic potential in liver cancer therapy.

Keywords: Exosome, Drug Delivery System, Low-intensity ultrasound, Hypoxia, Curcumin

1. Introduction

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), the most common liver cancer, is the fifth leading cancer worldwide[1]. In the early stages of cancer, surgical resection and liver transplantation are encouraged. Nevertheless, only 5 % to 15 % of HCC patients can benefit from surgery due to poor prognosis. Treatment of advanced stages includes chemotherapy and immunotherapy. However, these options contain systemic toxicity, side effects, and drug inefficacy, especially when delivered in the wrong locations. Therefore, diverse organic and inorganic nanomaterials have been researched to reduce the off-target effect. While drug-loaded nanoparticles in the bloodstream are not easily discharged in human bodies and are rapidly eliminated by phagocytosis, target specificity and controlled release therapy reveal their enormous potential in drug delivery[2].

In recent years, cell-secreted naturally occurring nanoparticles called exosomes have received widespread attention as a new-generation drug delivery platform due to their exceptional biocompatibility and ability to avoid mononuclear clearance mechanisms[3]. Sized 40 to 150 nm, exosomes can carry multiple biological contents, including proteins, nucleic acids, lipids, and sugars, that can be transferred to a recipient cell, mediating cell-to-cell communications[4]. Pioneering studies have already explored the opportunity for utilizing exosomes as a drug delivery vesicle, delivering gene/drug encapsulated exosomes to the target site[5]. Despite the promise, the current exosome-based delivery systems are still in their infancy, with two major problems requiring further research : (A) production of exosomes should meet sufficient abundance, and (B) naturally-derived exosomes should further develop target specificity. Recent studies have revealed that cancer under a hypoxic microenvironment increases the release of exosomes for their survival[6]. Hypoxia could also impact the properties of exosomes, which play a crucial role in cancer progression[7]. However, only a few studies have focused on utilizing hypoxically modified exosomes in drug delivery[8]. Moreover, exosomes are well known for their homotropic feature, where vesicles can travel back to their mother cell lines[9]. This intrinsic ability offers an additional mechanism for extending cancer targeting capability.

In order to further utilize exosomes as site-specific nanoparticles, exogenous stimuli were implemented to control drug releases precisely. Focused ultrasound with microbubbles produces thermal, mechanical, and radiation forces that can stimulate drug particles near exposed areas[10]. However, the relatively large size prohibits microbubbles from penetrating the blood vessels and, therefore, into the cancer cells[11]. To overcome this limitation, low-intensity ultrasounds (LIUS) without cavitation or contrast agents were implemented. LIUS-induced hyperthermia and/or mechanical stress promoted clathrin-mediated endocytosis, enhancing the penetration of drug molecules into the tumor cells[12]. Based on this evidence, the role of low-intensity ultrasound, given continuously (LICUS), to promote exosome enrichment near target sites was investigated.

Herein, this research demonstrates the design of a delivery system for HCC cancer therapy using an exosome derived from the hypoxic HepG2 liver cancer cells combined with LICUS and curcumin. Curcumin is a component of *Curcuma longa* (turmeric plant), which displays anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, and anti-cancer activities against multiple cancer cell lines[13]. Using exosomes, increased solubility, stability, and bioavailability of hydrophobic curcumin were discovered[14]. The anti-cancer effects elicited by LICUS and curcumin-loaded exosomes were tested on homotropic HCC cancers. The combined drug delivery platform displayed unique superiority, including (i) utilizing naturally occurring exosomes with excellent biocompatibility and safety; (ii) hypoxia-induced sufficient exosome abundance; (iii) LICUS-mediated non-invasive targeting specificity to achieve promising therapeutic potentials in clinical practice.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Exosome characterization

2.1.1. Exosome isolation

Exosomes were isolated from supernatants of SK-OV-3 (human ovarian cancer cells), RAW264.7 (mouse macrophage cells), and normoxic/hypoxic HepG2 cell (human liver cancer cells) lines. Briefly, cells (described above) were grown to 70 % confluency in a 100 π culture dish before the media was replaced by exosome-free 10 % FBS media. After 24 hours, the media used for the separation of Exosomes was purified by syringe filtering to remove debris and apoptotic bodies. The isolation of exosomes was performed with the Total Exosome Isolation Reagent (from cell culture media) kit from Thermo Fisher Scientific. The isolation was performed according to the protocol of the supplier. All samples were centrifuged with the Optima L-100 XP Ultracentrifuge (with SW32Ti rotor) from

Beckman Coulter (CA, USA), and the exosome pellets (kit isolates) were resuspended in PBS and stored at -80 °C prior to use.

2.1.2. Exosome size exclusion purification

400 μ l of kit isolates were centrifuged at 1,500 g and 10,000 g for 10 and 20 min, then overlaid onto a qEV size exclusion column (Izon) and eluted with PBS. 400 μ l fractions were collected, and particle and protein concentrations were measured using TRPS and Bradford assay (Bio-Rad), respectively. The high particle and low protein fractions of the kit isolates were pooled and concentrated on an Amicon® Ultra-4 10 kDa nominal molecular weight centrifugal filter to a final volume of 200 μ l.

2.1.3. Tunable resistive pulse sensing (TRPS)

The size distribution and concentration of particles was analyzed with TRPS (qNano, Izon Science Ltd) using a NP100 nanopore at a 45 nm stretch. The concentration of particles was standardized by the multiple pressure calibration method using 80-100 nm carboxylated polystyrene beads at a concentration of 1.5×10^{11} particles/ml.

2.1.4. Transmission electron microscope (TEM) analysis

Briefly, 3 ml of exosome suspension was fixed in 100 μ l of 2 % paraformaldehyde. 2 μ l of this mix was transferred onto each of 2 Formvar-carbon coated electron microscopy grids. The grids were removed with stainless steel loops and excess fluid blotted gently on Whatman no.1 filter paper. Grids were left to dry and stored in appropriate grid storage boxes. Grids were observed with HT7800 transmission electron microscope (Hitachi, Japan) at 80 kV.

2.2. In vitro experiments

2.2.1. Cell culture and Hypoxia exposure

HepG2 human liver cancer cells, SK-OV-3 human ovarian cancer cells, AsPC-1 human pancreatic cancer cells, RAW264.7 mouse macrophage cells, and Chang human liver cells were cultured in DMEM and RPMI supplemented with 10 % FBS, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 μ g/ml streptomycin in a humidified 5 % CO₂ incubator at 37 °C.

CoCl₂, a commonly used hypoxia mimetic agent, artificially induces hypoxia by blocking the degradation of the HIF-1 α protein. For hypoxia exposure, HepG2 cells were serum-starved for 3 h and exposed to different concentrations (50, 100, 250, 500, 750 μ M) of CoCl₂ at 37 °C for 24 h.

2.2.2. MTT assay

Cell viability was determined based on the conversion of MTT to MTT-formazan by mitochondrial enzymes. Briefly, cells were seeded into a 12-well plate at a density of 2×10^5 cells/well in 1 ml of medium in triplicate, stabilized to grow, and then treated with various concentrations of CoCl₂ (100, 250, 500, 750 μ M), curcumin, Pbs-Cur, N-Exo-Cur, and H-Exo-Cur with or without ultrasound. After 24 h of incubation at 37 °C, 100 μ l MTT solution (5 mg/ml stock) was added to the cells and incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. The medium was removed carefully, and then 150 μ l dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added to resolve the blue formazan in living cells. Finally, the absorbance was read at 540 nm with a SYNERGY HTX multi-mode reader (BioTek, VT, USA).

2.2.3. Western blot analysis

Cells (3×10^5 cells/well) in 3 ml of medium were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a 60 π culture dish. The cells were then washed twice with ice-cold PBS, and the total cell lysates were prepared in a lysis buffer containing 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.4), 150 mM NaCl, 1 % Triton X-100, 50 mM NaF, 5 mM sodium pyrophosphate, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM DTT, 0.1 mM PMSF, and 0.5 % protease inhibitor cocktail. The whole-cell lysates were centrifuged ($12,000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4 °C) to remove cellular debris. The protein

concentration was determined by the Lowry method using a Bio-Rad DC protein assay kit. For western blot analysis, cell lysates and purified exosomes containing equal amounts of protein (40 μg) were resolved by 8–15% SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and then transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes. The blots were blocked with a solution containing 5 % skim milk in Tris-buffered saline with 0.05% Tween 20 (TBST) for 1 h at room temperature and treated with primary antibodies in TBST overnight. Membranes were washed for 1 h with TBST and further probed with HRP-conjugated anti-mouse and anti-rabbit secondary antibodies in TBST for 1 h at room temperature. Finally, the immune complexes were visualized using an ECL detection system according to the manufacturer's protocols.

2.2.4. LICUS: Ultrasound Apparatus

For ultrasound treatment, cells were seeded in a 60 π quartz culture dish and placed in the water above the transducer in a horizontal position. The ultrasound wave was produced by Digisonic generators (Chungwoo medical, Inc., Korea). The frequencies of 1.0 MHz for in vivo and 3.0 MHz for in vitro with 360 mW/cm^2 intensity were treated for 15 min. The focal length was about 5 cm.

2.2.5. Curcumin encapsulation

Curcumin was encapsulated inside SK-OV-3, RAW264.7, and normoxic/hypoxic HepG2 cell secreted exosomes. To load a therapeutic drug with the exosomes (1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$), curcumin (25 μM in vitro, 30 μM in vivo) was gently mixed at a ratio of 1:1 w/w. To disrupt the exosome bilayer, sonication (Bandelin sonoplus HD 2070, Landsberger, Berlin) was performed at 20 % amplitude, 6 cycles of 30 s on/off three minute cooling period between each cycle. Subsequently, the mixture was incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h to allow the exosome membrane to recover. Moreover, it was observed that the membrane of exosomes remained well-preserved when curcumin was encapsulated in them via sonication (Fig S1). The curcumin encapsulation efficiency (EE) was calculated using the following formula :

$$\frac{\text{Total amount of H_Exo_Cur} - \text{amount of curcumin in the supernatnat}}{\text{Total amount of H_Exo_Cur}} \times 100 \%$$

The curcumin absorbance inside exosomes was determined using a SYNERGY HTX multi-mode reader (BioTek, VT, USA) at 450 nm. Pbs-Cur and all Exo-Cur samples were mixed with an equal volume of PBS to achieve a final concentration.

2.2.6. Curcumin release with or without LICUS

N-Exo-Cur and H-Exo-Cur were placed in the dialysis tubes to observe curcumin release after encapsulation. Dialysis tubes contained 4 ml PBS with different pH values (pH 7.0 and 5.0) and 0.1 % Triton X-100. All tubes were placed in a water bath at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. At each time interval, 200 μl of dialysate was collected and replaced with the same amount of fresh supplemented media. The concentration of released curcumin was detected by measuring the fluorescence with a SYNERGY HTX multi-mode reader (BioTek, VT, USA).

In all experiments, the cumulative release of the curcumin fraction was calculated based on the standard curve.

2.2.7. Detection of apoptosis by flow cytometry

Apoptotic cell death was detected by flow cytometry using the annexin V-FITC/PI double-labeling method. HepG2 cells were seeded at 2×10^5 cells/ml in a 60 π culture dish and treated with Pbs-Cur, N-Exo-Cur, and H-Exo-Cur with or without ultrasound. After incubation for 24 h, the cells were harvested, washed twice with PBS, trypsinized, and collected by centrifugation. After resuspension in 100 μl 1 \times binding buffer, the cells were incubated with 7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ annexin V-FITC and 7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ PI at room temperature in the dark for 1 h. The samples were analyzed using a MUSE Annexin V & Dead Cell Kit and a Muse cell analyzer (both from Merck Millipore, Danvers, MA, USA).

2.2.8. RT-PCR

Total RNA was extracted from cultured cells using TRI reagent. A cDNA was synthesized from 0.2 μ g total RNA using M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Fermentas, MD, USA). The specific primers for RT-PCR included the following: HIF-1 α forward 5'-CCCAATGTCGGAGTTTGGAAAA-3' and reverse 5'-GCACCAAGCAGGTCATAGGT-3'; and CD63, forward 5'-GCGGTGGAAGGA GGAATGAA-3' and reverse 5'-AGCCCCCTG-GATTATGGTCT-3' and Alix, forward 5'-CCCTG GATGTGATGGTGTCC-3' and reverse 5'-CCTGTTGCTGTCCAAGTTGC-3' and TSG101, forward 5'-CGGAGAGCCAGCTCAA-GAAA-3' and reverse 5'-CGGAGAGCCAGCTCAAGAAA-3'. Real-time PCR was performed using an ABI prism 7500 Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA) with SYBR-Green PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA). The PCR reaction was carried out for 40 thermal cycles. PCR products were visualized on a 1 % agarose gel by ethidium bromide staining. GAPDH was used as a loading control.

2.2.9. Migration assay

HepG2 cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^5 cells/well into 24-well dishes. After 24 h, a wound scratch was made on a 200 μ l pipette tip on the cells and treated with Pbs-Cur, N-Exo-Cur, and H-Exo-Cur with or without ultrasound. The cells were maintained at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. All images were captured after 24 h, or 48 h, to estimate the area occupied by migratory cells. The migration capacity was calculated using $[\Delta \text{ area/area (0 h)}] \times 100\%$.

2.2.10. Transwell invasion assay

For transwell invasion assay, the upper transwell chamber was coated with growth factor-reduced Matrigel (Corning, AZ, USA). Then, 5×10^5 HepG2 cells were diluted in 500 μ l serum-free DMEM medium and treated with Pbs-Cur, N-Exo-Cur, and H-Exo-Cur with or without ultrasound. DMEM medium containing 10 % FBS was added to the lower chamber as a chemoattractant. After 24 h or 48 h, cells on the upper surface of the membrane were removed using a cotton swab, and invaded cells were fixed with 75 % Methanol for 30 min at room temperature, followed by 0.25 % crystal violet staining (Sigma-Aldrich; Merck KGaA, MO, USA) for 1 h at room temperature.

2.2.11. Confocal microscopy

HepG2 cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^5 cells/ml on 12 well culture slides and allowed to adhere overnight. CD63-labeled or TSG101-labeled N-Exo-Cur, H-Exo-Cur, both with or without ultrasound, and Pbs-Cur were co-cultured with the HepG2 cells for 12 h, respectively. After 12 h, cells were washed three times with PBS, fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde for 15 min, and blocked with a solution containing 1 % BSA. Then, slides were FITC-conjugated anti-mouse and Cy3-conjugated anti-rabbit secondary antibodies in PBS for 1 h at room temperature. Pbs-Cur associated mean fluorescence intensity was analyzed using a fluorescence spectrophotometer at an excitation wavelength of 488 nm and an emission wavelength of 530 nm. The slides were washed three times before staining with DAPI. Images were taken on an LSM-800 (Carl Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) and analyzed with NIH Image J software. To study the internalization mechanism of the H-Exo-Cur-US, specific endocytic inhibitors, including chlorpromazine (30 μ M CPZ) were used to pretreat the HepG2 cells for 1 h. The following confocal procedure was identical.

2.3. In vivo experiments

2.3.1. animal model (Xenograft)

The Athymic nude mice (5 weeks, female, 18-20 g body weight) were obtained from Koatech Inc. (Gyeonggi-do, KOREA). A total of 15 Athymic nude mice were housed under controlled temperature (24 ± 1 $^{\circ}$ C), relative humidity (45~55 %), and artificial 12 h light-dark cycle lighting, with water and standard food ad libitum. As an anesthetic, Zoletil 50 (Tiletamine + Zolazepam) and Rompun (Xylazine) were purchased from VSP (Kyunggi-

do, Korea). Athymic nude mice were subcutaneously injected at the right flanks with 0.1 ml Matrigel and 0.1 ml HepG2 cells (1×10^7 cells/ml). When the tumor reached a size of 60-70 mm³, the tumor-bearing mice were randomly assigned to different groups and ready for an experiment. The Pbs-Cur or H-Exo-Cur were injected into the caudal vein. A first ultrasound was introduced 0.5 h prior to H-Exo-Cur injection. A second ultrasound was performed at 10 h post injection. This procedure was followed every 3 days. A tumor volume & weight, survival rate, and body weight were observed every 3 days. After 28 days of treatment, the tumor was fixed with 10 % formalin and stored at 4 °C until analysis. All animal experiments were approved by the Committee of Animal Experiments in the College of Medicine, Kyung Hee University (KHSASP-22-380). Five weeks old female Athymic nude mouse were bought from KOATECH (Kyunggi-do, Korea).

2.3.2. Hematoxylin and Eosin staining

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) solutions, formic acid, and 3,3'-diaminobenzidine-tetrahydrochloride hydrate (DAB) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). For histological observation, the tumors (Control, Pbs-Cur, H-Exo-Cur-US sample) were resected and immediately fixed with 10 % formalin, followed by dehydration with increasing concentrations of ethanol (70 %, 96 %, and 100 %) and decalcification with 10 % formic acid. Samples were embedded in paraffin, sectioned, and stained with H&E for morphological examination. The samples were treated with DAB and 0.5 % hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂ in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.6). Imaging was performed by fluorescence microscopy (IX73, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) with a color CCD camera (DP80, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan).

2.4. Statistical analysis

Experimental results are expressed as means \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) obtained from at least three independent experiments. The statistical significance of data was analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the R program suite (version 3.2.4; <http://www.r-project.org>). A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant; individual p-values (* p < 0.05 ; ** p < 0.01) are indicated in figures.

3. Results

3.1. Optimization of CoCl₂ dose to induce hypoxia on HepG2 cells

Cobalt chloride (CoCl₂) artificially mimics hypoxia by blocking the degradation of the HIF-1 α protein. To investigate the role of CoCl₂ on cell viability, different concentrations of CoCl₂ were treated against HepG2 cells in a dose-dependent manner. The cell viability reduced to 87.1 ± 4.1 %, 82.8 ± 0.6 %, 70.0 ± 2.2 %, and 54.1 ± 1.8 %, after exposure to 100, 250, 500, and 750 μ M of CoCl₂, respectively (Fig 1A). To confirm CoCl₂-induced hypoxia, the expression level of HIF-1 α protein was observed by western blot. As hypoxia elevates the Caveolin-1 protein, which links to calcium-binding S100P, the expressions of Caveolin-1 and S100A4 were also investigated[15]. HIF-1 α and Caveolin-1 protein levels increased dose-dependently, indicating a hypoxic microenvironment in HepG2 cells (Fig 1B, C). Among different concentrations treated, 500 μ M showed the highest HIF-1 α and Caveolin-1 protein levels. 500 μ M also successfully elevated the expression of the S100A4 protein (Fig 1D). When treated with a concentration of 750 μ M, most cells died, resulting in a weak band. Therefore, the concentration at 500 μ M was selected in the follow-up study. In addition, after CoCl₂ treatment, cell morphology shrank, and apoptotic bodies were shown (Fig S2). All these results indicated that CoCl₂ could induce hypoxia in HepG2 cells.

3.2. Characterization of Exosomes from Hypoxic (H-Exos) and Normoxic (N-Exos) HepG2 cells

Cancer cells generally produce more exosomes than non-cancerous cells due to deprived nutrients and the need for intercellular information. In hypoxic conditions, under extreme deficiencies in nutrients and oxygen, cancer cells further increase exosome production for survival. To understand the molecular mechanism behind increased exosome

production in HCC cancers undergoing hypoxic cellular stress, HepG2 cells were treated with 500 μM of CoCl_2 , and the expression levels of proteins related to exosome biogenesis were analyzed using western blots. Rab27a and Rab7, part of a large family of small GTPases, act as key regulators of exosome secretion. Increased Rab27a and decreased Rab7 levels increased exosome production in ovarian cancer cells under hypoxia[16]. Consistent with the previous studies, upregulated Rab27a and downregulated Rab7 proteins in HepG2 cells were observed (Fig 2A).

Exosomes were collected from hypoxic (H-Exos) and normoxic (N-Exos) conditioned media of the HepG2 cells. Briefly, they were isolated and purified using isolation kits and ultracentrifugation, as described. Common exosomal markers, such as CD63, Alix, and TSG101, were characterized in both transcription and translation levels to observe successful vesicle isolation. All proteins were elevated in either exosome compared to the whole cell lysate (Fig 2B, C). However, noticeable amounts of elevation were observed from H-Exos than from N-Exos. Agreeing that all samples were quantified for western blot analysis, this data indicates that hypoxic conditions induce more exosome production from HepG2 cells than in normoxic conditions.

Next, proteins associated with the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and mitochondria were analyzed inside exosomes. While HepG2 lysates showed cytochrome C and calnexin expression, no expressions were found on either exosome sample (Fig 2D). The lack of ER and mitochondrial proteins inside exosome preparations indicated that the isolated vesicles were relatively free of cell debris.

Exosomes resemble lots of their contents from parent cells. Changes in molecular context by hypoxia might be reflected in cell-secreted exosomes. To confirm exosomes in hypoxic conditions, a hypoxia-associated protein inside H-Exos was analyzed. Previous results (Fig 1) confirmed an essential relationship between CoCl_2 -induced hypoxia and HIF-1 α protein. Similarly, the HIF-1 α protein was expressed in both H-Exos and hypoxic mother cells (Fig 2E). No expression was shown between normoxic HepG2 cells or N-Exos. As seen in the TEM results of N-Exos (control exosome), H-Exos, and H-Exo-Cur, it was confirmed that induction of hypoxia led to an increase in the observed amount of exosomes compared to the control group (Fig 2F).

All these observations imply hypoxia-induced alterations in liver cancer and how such stress can impact cell-secreted exosomes. As the quantity of exosome production has always been issued in exosome-based drug delivery, hypoxia might provide an alternate solution through increasing exosome production. Also, altered protein content inside H-Exos might highlight enhanced uptake specificity towards target cells.

3.3. Exosomes can increase the solubility and stability of hydrophobic curcumin

Curcumin is a hydrophobic component of *Curcuma longa* (turmeric plant), used as a chemotherapeutic drug to cure colon, skin, and intestinal cancers. To determine the concentration of curcumin, HepG2 cells were treated with the drug in a dose-dependent manner (Fig 3A). Considering that too much cell death induced by curcumin might disturb analyzing/comparing the therapeutic results, 25 μM with about 20 % cell death was selected. Next, 25 μM of curcumin was either encapsulated inside exosomes (H-Exo-Cur, N-Exo-Cur) or mixed in an equal volume of PBS (Pbs-Cur). Briefly, ultrasonication created pores on exosomal membranes where drugs could flow in, and drug-encapsulated exosomes (H-Exo-Cur, N-Exo-Cur) were incubated for 30 minutes to enrich stable loading. The drug absorbance was measured using a UV-vis spectrophotometer. The encapsulation efficiencies of N-Exo-Cur and H-Exo-Cur samples were calculated to be 52.33% and 57.25%, respectively. All three spectra showed no difference in the position or the shape of the absorbance band (Fig 3B). However, at 450 nm, absorption spectra of drug-encapsulated exosomes showed a much lower peak value than that of Pbs-Cur. Exosomal membranes might have disturbed the photon absorption of curcumin, indicating successful drug encapsulation.

Previous studies have described increased stability and solubility of curcumin when encapsulated inside an exosome[14]. To observe a similar trend, the stabilities of

curcumin were measured (Fig 3C). During the same period, Pbs-Cur degraded quickly, while almost constant drug concentration was observed from drug-encapsulated exosomes (Pbs-Cur at 150 min, 53.2 ± 4.0 % vs. H-Exo-Cur at 150 min, 93.2 ± 3.2 %; Fig 3C). Next, HepG2 cells were treated with curcumin to observe drug solubilities. Chang.et.al reported that curcumin inhibits HCC cells by downregulating miR-21 and upregulating TIMP3 expression levels[17]. Likely, curcumin-treated HepG2 cells showed increased TIMP3 expression, indicating successful drug treatment (Fig 3D, E). Interestingly, about 1.5 times higher. This result indirectly supports increased drug solubility when encapsulated inside exosomes. Increased solubility might have increased drug concentration and, therefore, enhanced TIMP3 expression.

Exosomes are incorporated into recipient cells through endocytosis and degraded within lysosomes. Lysosomes commonly exhibit pH 4–5 values, bursting exosomal membranes and releasing encapsulated drugs when internalized. To examine pH-dependent curcumin release, the drug concentrations of H-Exo-Cur and N-Exo-Cur were observed periodically with different pH values (Fig 3F). Briefly, drug-encapsulated exosomes were placed in PBS and treated with different amounts of HCl to match the following pH values. At pH 7.0 (extracellular environment), H-Exo-Cur and N-Exo-Cur released less than 10 % of the loaded curcumin within 60 h, which, after 10 h, constant release profiles were observed. This suggests that curcumin was well protected inside the exosome, and only a tiny amount of drugs would be leaked during blood circulation. In contrast, rapid and massive curcumin release was observed at pH 5.0 (lysosome), almost 2 or 3 times greater than pH 7.0. This indicates that drug-encapsulated exosomes entering cancer cells and lysosomes will burst drug release affecting cell viability. Fig 3G showed that the TEM results of N-Exos (control exosome), N-Exo-Cur, and H-Exo-Cur, it was observed that the size of the samples containing Curcumin showed a slight increase or exhibited a black color surrounding the membrane, compared to the control group.

All results supported successful loading and enhanced therapeutic effects of curcumin-loaded exosomes compared to Pbs-Cur. Yet in drug loading and pH-dependent releasing process, no differences were observed between H-Exo-Cur and N-Exo-Cur.

3.4. Parent HepG2 cells preferably fused with Homologous exosomes

Homo-tropism, where secreted particles can travel back to their parent cell, is a unique feature of exosomes[18]. To evaluate whether HepG2 cells prefer parent cell-derived vesicles, exosomes from the SK-OV-3 ovarian cancer cell and RAW 264.7 macrophage cell were also isolated. All exosomes showed elevated levels of CD63, indicating successful isolation (Fig 2B, 4A). No exosomes had cytotoxic effects on cancer cell viability or morphology (Fig 4B, C).

If exosomes induce no cytotoxic effect, and if the same amount of drug is deposited inside, the cancer cell with the highest uptake will result in the most cell death. This data will indirectly indicate homotropic targeting bias carried by liver cancer cell-secreted particles. Therefore, all exosomes were encapsulated with the same concentration of curcumin, and the therapeutic effects of each Exo-Cur were compared (Fig 4D). Like before (Fig 3A), curcumin induced about 20 % of cell death (Pbs-Cur, 83.0 ± 2.3 %; Fig 4D). Exo-Cur from normoxic liver cancer showed higher cell death than those from ovarian cancer, suggesting special homotropic characteristics of parent cancer cells and derived exosomes (N-HepG2-Exos, 68.0 ± 2.4 % vs. N-SK-OV-3-Exos, 90.4 ± 1.5 %; Fig 4D). Macrophage-derived exosomes bear immune-protective signals, decreasing drug clearance before reaching a target, making them suitable for drug delivery[19]. Exo-Cur from immune cells was effective, as more cell death was induced than Pbs-Cur (Pbs-Cur, 83.0 ± 2.3 % vs. N-RAW264.7-Exos, 78.0 ± 0.5 %; Fig 4D). However, the unique mechanism or peptides that increase uptake efficiency on macrophage exosomes seems less potent than exosomes carrying homotropic features. (N-RAW264.7-Exos, 78.0 ± 0.5 % vs. N-HepG2-Exos, 68.0 ± 2.4 %; Fig 4D) Hypoxic exosomes showed the most significant inhibitory effect (N-HepG2-Exos, 68.0 ± 2.4 % vs. H-HepG2-Exos, 62.1 ± 0.4 %; Fig 4D). Two possible explanations might back up these results. As mentioned above (Fig 2), exosomes from hypoxic cancer possessed increased

amounts/concentration and altered protein composition. This might have affected their ability in cell targeting. This result reinforces enhanced exosome uptake through engineered parent-cell environments.

Next, to evaluate whether HepG2 exosomes prefer HepG2 cells in vice versa, therapeutic effects of N-Exo-Cur and H-Exo-Cur on AsPC-1 pancreatic cancer cells and SK-OV-3 cells were compared. Exo-Cur from hypoxic liver cancer cells induced a more substantial apoptotic effect on parent cell than against other cancer cells (H-Exo-Cur treated AsPC-1, 80.0 ± 3.3 %, vs. H-Exo-Cur treated SK-OV-3, 82.1 ± 1.6 %, vs. H-Exo-Cur treated HepG2, 61.5 ± 2.7 %; Fig 4E). Minor differences were found between H-Exo-Cur and N-Exo-Cur against multiple cell lines, suggesting hypoxically engineered targeting ability only functions when treated against parent cancer.

In all cases, homogeneous drug-encapsulated HepG2 exosomes showed the most suppressive effects against homogeneous HepG2 cell lines. Parent HepG2 cells and N-Exos or H-Exos fit for each other and therefore offer the therapeutic potential for being a “Trojan horse.” HepG2 exosomes can travel back to their parent cancer cell types and efficiently shuttle hydrophobic anticancer drugs.

3.5. LICUS promotes exosomes penetration through hyperthermia and mechanical stress

LICUS is a non-invasive medical treatment that delivers low intensity in the mode of continuous waves. Low-intensity ultrasound-treated therapy generally applies intensities from 20 to 1000 mW/cm² and frequencies from 1 to 3 MHz[20, 21]. In this experiment, the intensity of 360 mW/cm² and frequencies of both 1 and 3 MHz were tested. Schematic views of the LICUS apparatus are shown (Fig 5A). Both frequencies did not affect cell viability or morphology (Fig 5B, C).

The interaction between ultrasound and contrast agents creates shockwaves and cavitation near the target area, leading to nanoparticle-encapsulated drug release and cell membrane permeabilization[22]. Drug-release behavior in a static status was already shown (Fig 3F). To detect whether LICUS assistance can boost drug release, curcumin concentration after ultrasound exposure was measured. Briefly, both H-Exo-Cur and N-Exo-Cur were placed in the quartz dish to minimize ultrasound disturbance and were stimulated with frequencies of 1 or 3 MHz. As expected, without any contrast agents, the two frequencies had no additional effect on the drug-release behavior (Fig 5D).

In this research, the interaction between LICUS and exosomes was irrelevant without contrast agents. However, LICUS offers mechanical and thermal stimuli when placed near the target lesion, increasing drug uptake in cancer cells[20]. Therefore, the interaction between LICUS and target cells was studied. Among many biological effects ultrasound produces, hyperthermia (mild temperatures around 43 °C) increases blood flow and vascular permeability concentrating chemotherapeutic drugs within the heated region[23]. To evaluate whether LICUS can produce mild heat, local temperatures after ultrasound treatment were measured. Both 1 and 3 MHz successfully increased temperature up to 40 °C, a defined temperature for hyperthermia (Fig 5E).

Nevertheless, both 1 and 3 MHz carry different merits. 3 MHz with a shorter wavelength can generate more stimuli per given time, while 1 MHz with a longer wavelength can promote deeper penetration. In in vitro environments, where LICUS stimulates cells directly, 3 MHz with more stimulation cycles was more favorable (the highest temperature from 3 MHz was observed). However, as depth penetration is required in vivo, 1 MHz was selected for later in vivo experiments.

Next, to evaluate whether an interaction between LICUS and target cells can promote exosome uptake, confocal laser scanning microscopy was used to track the intracellular localization of exosomes (Fig S3). Cell nuclei were labeled with DAPI (blue) signals, and exosomal membranes were labeled with common exosome marker TSG101-FITC (green) signals. Fluorescent microscopy confirmed that exosomes were successfully fused within the parent cancer cell, as green fluorescence was well dispersed within the cytoplasm. As expected, higher fluorescence from H-Exos than N-Exos was observed. This data also indirectly supports previous MTT results (Fig 4D), where H-Exo-Cur showed a higher

apoptotic effect than N-Exo-Cur. Hypoxically engineered exosomes with homotropic features were preferentially uptaken, and when camouflaged with hydrophobic drugs, they successfully tricked and attacked the parent cancer cells.

Exosome uptake was further enhanced by ultrasound treatment. To highlight, LICUS-stimulated N-Exos showed higher merged signals than H-Exos without stimulation. Exogenous stimuli seem to elevate vesicle uptake more than innately occurring endocytosis. Unsurprisingly, adding LICUS treatment to H-Exos, which already showed excellent targeting efficiency, resulted in the highest cell localization. To emphasize, compared to naturally-secreted N-Exos, hypoxically-modified H-Exos with LICUS treatment showed almost twice the accumulation near the target cancer area.

LICUS, used in this experiment, was not directly involved with the exosome and drug release behavior. However, multiple biological effects created by ultrasound can target cancer cells and promote vesicle uptake. This will provide an additive strategy to deliver therapeutic cargo.

3.6. LICUS-induced Exosomes uptake is mediated mainly by the clathrin-mediated pathway

Clathrin forms rounded vesicles at the cytoplasm to selectively sort cargo near the cell membrane for intracellular trafficking. LICUS-triggered clathrin pathways effectively induced bisphosphonate uptake and anticancer activity in breast cancer cells[12, 23]. To demonstrate if the LICUS acts specifically on the clathrin pathway to induce exosome uptake, chlorpromazine (CPZ) was treated on HepG2 cells to block clathrin-mediated pathways transiently. Western blot analysis was used to characterize two important endocytosis routes, clathrin and caveolin. As expected, CPZ-treated cancer cells showed inhibited levels of clathrin protein, while no difference was observed in the Caveolin-1/Caveolin-mediated pathway (Fig 6A).

Next, confocal laser scanning microscopy was used to validate the intracellular localization of exosomes (Fig 6B). Cell nuclei were labeled with DAPI (blue) signals, and exosomal membranes were labeled with common exosome marker CD63-Cy3 (red) signals. Similar to the previous result (Fig S3), LICUS-triggered H-Exos were well dispersed within the cytoplasm: purple (merged) fluorescence was easily spotted. However, pre-incubation with CPZ after ultrasound stimulation reduced cellular uptake of H-Exos up to ~50%. When the LICUS-induced clathrin pathway was inhibited, large numbers of exosomes were not taken up by the cancer cells. This indicates that endocytosis mediated by clathrin was dominant in the LICUS-triggered cellular uptake, similar to a previously reported internalization mechanism of extracellular vesicles.

3.7. Cellular Uptake and Cytotoxicity of a homologous hypoxic exosome and LICUS

Off-target toxicity is a severe defect of conventional chemotherapy undergoing clinical trials[24]. Likely, a similar amount of apoptosis was induced in cells treated with Pbs-Cur, whether cancer (Fig 4D, E) or normal (Fig 7A): ~15.6%. This off-target effect remains a significant barrier to curcumin-based clinical efficacy. Conversely, exosomes allow curcumin to reach a specific target, solving such problems. Designed Exo-Cur showed little or no effect on normal liver cells (Fig 7A), though a negligible amount of cell death might have been caused due to a small amount of curcumin left unencapsulated. A considerable amount of cell death was induced against parent cancer cells (Fig 7B).

Exosome-based drug delivery systems exert anti-cancer activity based on their intracellular accumulations. Exosome uptake near cancer nuclei, with or without ultrasound, has already been established (Fig S3, 6B). Therefore, the cellular uptake of curcumin-loaded exosomes was monitored using confocal microscopic analysis (Fig 7C). Cell nuclei were labeled with DAPI (blue) signals, exosomal membranes were labeled with common exosome marker CD63-Cy3 (red) signals, and pure Curcumins were detected with 530 nm (green) signals after excitation at 488 nm. All Exo-Cur (N-Exo-Cur, H-Exo-Cur, N-Exo-Cur-US, H-Exo-Cur-US) samples were preferentially taken up by the HepG2 cells, and curcumin was successfully dissociated from the exosome and distributed well through the cytoplasm and nuclei of the cancer cells. Although the same amount of drug was loaded

inside all Exo-Cur samples, the cell with the most exosome uptake showed the highest curcumin amount (curcumin dissociation) and green fluorescence.

Relatively high fluorescence was observed in the case of Pbs-Cur. Please note that Pbs-Cur administered in this research was treated directly to cancer cells. In clinical studies, after oral administration, curcumin is digested into the stomach, passes the intestinal walls, into the liver for detoxification, and finally into the bloodstream. During such a process, only a smaller amount of curcumin (than the initial administration) is delivered to target cancer. Exosomes can increase the stability and solubility of hydrophobic curcumin[14]. Most importantly, curcumin encapsulated inside exosomes will maintain a similar amount to the initial concentration, and therefore, a higher amount of curcumin will be dispersed within cell nuclei, as shown in confocal results. This result proves the excellent therapeutic potential of designed nano-systems against liver cancer cells.

Cell apoptosis according to the order of curcumin fluorescence was also observed in MTT results (Fig 7B). Cancer cells treated with all Exo-Cur samples induced superior cell death than samples treated with the same amount of Pbs-Cur (Fig 4D, 7B). Especially H-Exos/H-Exo-Cur than N-Exos/N-Exo-Cur, more exactly H-Exos/H-Exo-Cur with LICUS, was well dispersed within the cell nuclei/cytoplasm (Fig S3, 7C). Likely, H-Exo-Cur than N-Exo-Cur, more exactly H-Exo-Cur with LICUS, induced the highest cell death against parent HepG2 cells (Fig 4D, 7B).

In every result in this research, H-Exos showed more precise targeting towards HepG2 cells than N-Exos. With LICUS, H-Exos were more preferentially located near cell nuclei, and H-Exo-Cur induced higher apoptosis than N-Exo-Cur. Therefore, in the follow-up study, N-Exo-Cur with LICUS was not investigated. Though, N-Exo-Cur was still investigated to compare the superiority of H-Exo-Cur.

3.8. LICUS accelerates the anti-cancer activity of H-Exo-Cur *in vitro*

HCCs are one of the fatal malignant liver cancers worldwide. Although chemotherapy is currently used, exosome-based drug delivery systems are being researched to cure HCC patients. Exo-Cur exerts anti-cancer effects by intercellularly tricking cancer cells into accumulating (drug-loaded) exosomes.

The therapeutic potential of H-Exo-Cur with LICUS has been established (Fig 7). To specifically examine how Exo-Cur induces cancer cell death, an annexin V-FITC/PI double staining was performed (Fig 8A). Every four spots on the dot plot represent the percentage of lived (annexin V-negative/PI-negative), early apoptotic (annexin V-positive/PI-negative), late apoptotic (annexin V-positive/PI-positive), and necrotic (annexin V-negative/PI-positive) cells. H-Exo-Cur treated early apoptosis cells rate increased significantly, about eight times compared to Pbs-Cur. When ultrasound was applied, the percentage increased from 8.35 % to 13.55 %. Likewise, H-Exo-Cur treated late apoptotic cell rate showed about two times increase compared to Pbs-Cur. With ultrasound, the percentage grew from 25.9 % to 31.3 %. Compared to early/late apoptosis, H-Exo-Cur with or without ultrasound had a small or almost no effect on necrotic cell rate. Next, the expression levels of proteins that play a vital role in apoptosis were observed (Fig 8B). H-Exo-Cur with ultrasound upregulated the expression of Bax, Caspase-3, Bim, and PARP proteins and downregulated the expression of Bcl-2 protein.

Metastasis, where cancer cells travel away from the original tumor and form a new tumor in other organs or tissues, is a complex challenge that all cancer-targeting drugs are faced with. Anti-cancer effects on cancer cell invasion and migration were measured. To measure invasion, a transwell assay was performed (Fig 8C). Briefly, cancer cells were plated onto the upper layer of the Matrigel membrane matrix and, after drug treatment, incubated for 24 h. The group treated with H-Exo-Cur and ultrasound showed the minimum number of invasive cells, approximately 43.7 % less than the Pbs-Cur. To determine proliferation, wound healing or scratch assay was acquired (Fig 8D). Briefly, drug-treated cancer cells were scratched and incubated for 24 and 48 h. Setting a dotted red line as a base, the numbers of all samples that crossed the line were less than the control. Moreover, the proliferation rate of all samples was suppressed approximately 1.5 times more in 48 h

than in 24 h. As expected, H-Exo-Cur with ultrasound showed the most suppressive effect: migration of HepG2 cells was reduced by approximately 15.9 % and 22.8 % less than Pbs-Cur at 24 h and 48 h.

Cancer cell migration and invasion are often linked to epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). EMT markers were determined using the expression level of migration-associated proteins (Fig 8E). Without any treatment, liver cancer cells revealed strong expressions in metastasis (S100A4) and MMP (MMP-2, MMP-9) markers. In previous reports, the hallmark of EMT suppression is the upregulation of E-cadherin and the downregulation of N-cadherin[25]. Pbs-Cur treated samples showed no noticeable effect on these proteins. After being treated with H-Exo-Cur and ultrasound, the expression of metastasis and MMP makers were significantly suppressed, the expression of the epithelial maker (E-Cadherin) was upregulated, and the expression of the mesenchymal maker (N-Cadherin) was downregulated.

In all cases, LICUS-triggered H-Exo-Cur showed enormous anti-cancer effects in vitro. Preferred uptake by homo-tropism, increased amount and enhanced internalization by hypoxic engineering, with hyperthermic and mechanical stress prompted by LICUS, successfully induced cancer cell death and suppressed cancer cell invasion and migration.

3.9. LICUS combined H-Exo-Cur effectively improves the anti-cancer activity in vivo

The ability of hypoxia to increase exosome production and, with LICUS, selectively target homotropic cancers offers therapeutic opportunities for the treatment of liver cancer. To test this hypothesis in vivo studies, the cancer-targeting ability of H-Exo-Cur with LICUS was investigated using Athymic nude mice bearing HepG2 cancer as a model.

Previous in vitro results showed excellent intercellular permeability of N-Exo or N-Exo-Cur. However, due to extensive time consumption and low quantity, naturally-occurring exosomes were far from meeting standard exosome-based nano-therapy in many in vivo experiments and clinical applications. Therefore, to acquire a sufficient amount, exosomes from hypoxic cells were taken into consideration because of the abundant source, high yield, and enhanced targeting ability. Moreover, due to the low bioavailability of curcumin, high doses of curcumin were treated to achieve a detectable anticancer effect in curcumin-treated mice: at 30 μ M, the cell viability was reduced to near IC50 (Fig 3A). Finally, as mentioned before, the ultrasound frequency parameters used in vitro (3 MHz) were adjusted for in vivo experiments (1 MHz) for deeper penetration.

For five weeks, cancer development was monitored, and treatment protocols were initiated as described (Fig 9A). Briefly, exosomes were injected after tumor implantation, with a curcumin concentration at 30 μ M in every 3 days for 30 days. To maximize ultrasound exposure, LICUS was treated twice. The first ultrasound was introduced 0.5 h prior to H-Exo-Cur injection, and the second stimulation was performed 10 h post H-Exo-Cur administration. On last day of the treatment, both Pbs-Cur and H-Exo-Cur groups exhibited noticeable inhibitory effects on cancer growth than the control (Fig 9B, C, D). The H-Exo-Cur-US treatment showed the most regression in tumor growth and an extended survival time (Fig 9E), improving hydrophobic curcumin treatment. This result demonstrates how efficient drug injection with nanoparticle encapsulation is. While Exo-Cur is concentrated near the target area, Pbs-Cur is exposed to many different body parts, causing various side effects. Moreover, curcumin is relatively unstable and insoluble in aqueous solutions. Therefore, as mentioned before, the drug concentration near the target site will be much less than the initial concentration. In summary, H-Exo-Cur combined with twice LICUS stimuli in specific areas inhibited cancer growth to a greater extent and improved the therapeutic effect of the original curcumin treatment.

H&E staining was performed on cancers collected from the mice to evaluate the in vivo anticancer effects (Fig 9F). The result further confirmed the superior anticancer efficacy of H-Exo-Cur with LICUS: H&E staining revealed apparent tissue damage caused by Exo-Cur injection.

The safety profiles of the designed nano-therapy were analyzed based on the weight changes and survival period experienced by mice. The body weight of the control group

decreased during the period, while no significant changes were caused in response to the following curcumin treatment (Fig 9G). Together, these data provide a relatively safe evaluation and high therapeutic efficacy of the designed nanoplateforms.

4. Discussion

In this study, exosomes were reprogrammed by inducing hypoxia on parent cancer cells and continuously stimulated by low-intensity ultrasound. Such modification and stimulation substantially improved exosome targeting and uptake efficiency, mainly through clathrin-mediated pathways. H-Exos were successfully fused with hydrophobic curcumin and effectively delivered into homotropic liver cancer with the help of LICUS. The nano-platform designed in this research provides a valuable future strategy for cancer-specific target therapy.

Hypoxia frequently occurs in cancer cells. Uncontrollable cell proliferation and abnormal tumor vessels reduce oxygen and nutrient transport, resulting in a hypoxic environment. So far, biological contents and effects of exosomes from HCC liver cancer under a low oxygen state have been reviewed. miR-1273f was upregulated in hypoxic HCC exosomes, enhancing the malignant phenotype of the normoxic HCC cells[6]. Upregulated miR-155 and miR23a inside hypoxic HCC exosomes were uptaken by HUVECS, promoting angiogenesis[26, 27].

Likely in this research, increased exosome secretion and altered protein composition were observed. Hypoxic and normoxic HepG2 cells showed different levels of Rab7 and Rab27a proteins. Compared to naturally occurring N-Exos, hypoxically engineered H-Exos showed elevated levels of common exosomal markers (CD63, Alix, TSG101). HIF-1 α contained in hypoxic HepG2 cells was also discovered inside secreted exosomes. H-Exos were more accumulated near cell nuclei/cytoplasm, and with LICUS, H-Exo showed almost twice the accumulation near the target cancer area compared to N-Exos. When loaded with curcumin, H-Exo-Cur exhibited higher anti-cancer effects: more curcumin near cell nuclei/cytoplasm, a greater number of apoptotic cells, and significantly suppressed cancer invasion or migration.

While most of this research focused on the application and phenomena of these altered exosomes near the target area, underlying structural alteration or mechanism behind exosomes changed by hypoxic conditions must be further investigated. Gong. et al. engineered natural MGC803 human gastric cancer exosomes by inducing an acidic (low-pH) microenvironment on donor cells. Lipidomic analyses found different lipid structures (especially higher glycerolipid composition) in these low-pH exosomes, impacting homologous interactions with target cells[28]. Therefore, more in-depth research on lipid structural analysis or membrane protein involved in hypoxic exosomes could help explain the mechanism behind exosome uptake in specific organs.

The uptake mechanism between parent cancer cells and homologous exosomes remains unclear. Exosomes might be particularly effective in targeting parent cells as they resemble lots of protein contents and composition from the cells they are from. Cancer exosomes fuse with cancer cells through lipid mixing, unique protein/receptor composition, or exosomal integrins[28, 29]. However, not all exosomes exhibit homotropic properties. Some researchers reported a similar accumulation of exosomes with their parent cells and cells of other origins, and therefore, the insufficient ability of homogenous exosomes to specifically target their parent cell line[30]. Currently, exosomes' biological properties from various source cells are still being unraveled and still need to be standardized.

In this research, homogenous HepG2 exosomes were preferentially uptaken by parent HepG2 cells. Both naturally occurring N-Exos and hypoxically engineered H-Exos were located near cancer cell nuclei/cytoplasm. When loaded with curcumin, N-Exo-Cur and H-Exo-Cur showed the most suppressive effect against parent HepG2 cells than against other cancer or normal cell lines. HepG2 cells were also preferentially fused with HepG2 exosomes. Compared to (curcumin encapsulated) ovarian cancer or macrophage

immune cell-secreted exosomes, N-Exo-Cur or H-Exo-Cur induced a more substantial apoptotic effect against parent liver cancer cells. In vivo studies showed reduced cancer volume/weight and H&E staining revealed cancer tissue damage caused by Exo-Cur injection. No noticeable changes in body weight and a more extended survival period experienced by Exo-Cur treated mice indicate the safety profiles of the designed nanoplateforms.

In vivo or clinical studies, biodistribution, metabolism, and clearance of exosomes remain major issues in exosome-based drug delivery. Despite the therapeutic efficacy, potential adverse effects should be further researched. Wang. et al. examined H&E analysis of the heart, liver, spleen, and kidney after treating blood serum-derived B-Exos (doxorubicin loaded) against the GL261 glioblastoma cell line[31]. All major organs of Exo-Dox treated mice were similar to unmedicated control groups, and no significant pathological changes were observed. Cheng. et al. detected biodistribution of HT1080 fibrosarcoma cells and HeLa cervical cancer cells exosomes using IVIS imaging systems[32]. While HT1080 exosomes were preferentially localized to tumor tissue, HeLa exosomes were abundantly presented near other organs. Likely, more studies should investigate the biodistribution of HepG2 exosomes: whether H-Exos/N-Exos can sufficiently colonize the parent cancer site and not other organs.

5. Conclusions

Taken together, this finding indicates the therapeutic effects of exosomes derived from hypoxic liver cancer cells loaded with hydrophobic curcumin and that low-intensity ultrasound can further enhance exosome uptake. A different way of utilizing ultrasound to promote vesicle endocytosis was investigated. The clathrin pathway activated by the low-intensity ultrasound had no relation with microbubble-cell interactions. Mild hyperthermia (between 42 °C and 43 °C) and mechanical stimulations created by LICUS were sufficient to promote exosome penetration. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study reporting the relationship between low-intensity ultrasound and hypoxic exosome-based drug delivery. The designed platform provides valuable future strategies to cure other cancer-related diseases.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, M.S. K., Y.J. K., K.-S. Y., and H.H. B.; methodology, M.S. K., Y.J. Y.; Formal analysis, M.S. K., Y.J. K.; Investigation, M.S. K., Y.J. K., C.Y. H., H.H. B. and Y.J. Y.; Writing-original draft, M.S. K., Y.J. K. and I.S. K.; Validation, M.H. S., S.K. K., K.-S. Y., I.S. K., H.H. B. and Y.J. Y.; Review and Editing, M.S. K., Y.J. K.; Data Curation, I.S. K., H.H. B., Y.J. Y.; Funding acquisition, I.S. K., H.H. B. and Y.J. Y.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by the Basic Science Research Program of the National Research Foundation of Korea (2021R1F1A1049054).

Institutional Review Board Statement: All animal experiments were approved by the Committee of Animal Experiments in the College of Medicine, Kyung Hee University (KHSASP-22-380), and were treated in strict accordance with the National Institutes of Health Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: In this section, please provide details regarding where data supporting reported results can be found, including links to publicly archived datasets analyzed or generated during the study. Please refer to suggested Data Availability Statements in section “MDPI Research Data Policies” at <https://www.mdpi.com/ethics>. If the study did not report any data, you might add “Not applicable” here.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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